

LIVED EXPERIENCES OF FILIPINO EMERGING ADULTS RECEIVING GRANDPARENT'S KINSHIP CARE

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Lived Experiences of Filipino Emerging Adults Receiving Grandparent's Kinship Care

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Abstract

This study dives into the various experiences of Filipino emerging adults receiving grandparent's kinship care. The researchers aim to answer the recommendation part of the study that was published in the year 2005 by Samia III in his research 'An Exploratory Study of the Lives of Filipino Grandparents Raising their Grandchildren through the research recommendation focusing on the perspective of the Filipino grandchildren raised by grandparents. The researchers have interviewed ten (10) Filipino emerging adults who fits the inclusion criteria of the study from Manggahan, Commonwealth, Quezon City. To gather the data and examine different perspectives, explore the values and beliefs, analyze the challenges faced, and determine the different coping strategies. Thus, highlights the themes: "Autonomy, Being and Courtesy, Dissonance and Endurance, and Freedom."

Keywords: *lived experiences, filipino emerging adults, grandparent's kinship care*

Introduction

The strong Filipino family ties give cultural importance to extended families wherein relatives step in to care for children in need. This refers to kinship care, which has been a prevalent practice in Filipino households for so many years due to a great sense of filial piety. Regardless of the numerous researches throughout the years about the value of kinship care, there is still limited information on the emotional and psychological aspects of these kinship relationships specifically on the perspectives of those who are receiving care.

Childhood and adolescence represent crucial periods requiring significant parental involvement and guidance, yet a substantial portion of Filipino youth today, about one-third, navigate these phases without both biological parents present. Data from the 2021 Young Adult Fertility and Sexuality Study (YAFSS) as cited from the University of the Philippines Population Institute (2022) indicates that only 67% of young people were raised by both parents, with figures declining to 65% among ages 15-19 and 68% among ages 20-24, marking a decline from previous years. The rise in youth raised by a single parent correlates with parental migration within the country during the youth's childhood. As support, the '2022 Survey on Overseas Filipinos' conducted by the Philippine Statistics Authority reveals that an estimated 1.96 million Filipinos are working abroad from April to September of the same year where CALABARZON ranks the highest distribution having 15.3%, following Central Luzon at 13.3%, Western Visayas 11.1%, and NCR 10.9%. This migration led to their children being left behind with their relatives in the Philippines.

Filipinos highlight the importance of filial piety or respect for elders and hiya or avoiding shame in Filipino culture, emphasizing their role in maintaining strong family unity according to Scroope in 2017. With this, grandparents ages 40 to 65 years old are the ones who often take responsibility for taking care of their grandchildren which also provides an explanation regarding Erik Erikson's Psychosocial Development in generativity versus stagnation, emphasizing the elder's satisfaction in contributing to the younger generation.

This study entitled 'Lived Experiences of Filipino Emerging Adults Receiving Grandparent's Kinship Care' aims to fill the research gap that was first noticed in the year 2005 by Samia III in his research 'An Exploratory Study of the Lives of Filipino Grandparents Raising their Grandchildren' through the research recommendation of focusing on the perspective of the Filipino grandchildren raised by grandparents.

Research Questions

The purpose of this qualitative study is to explore the lived experiences of Filipino emerging adults receiving grandparent kinship care. Specifically, this study aimed to:

1. Examine different perspectives of Filipino emerging adults regarding their grandparent care.
2. Explore the values and beliefs of the Filipino emerging adults raised by their grandparents.
3. Analyze the possible challenges faced by Filipino emerging adults who have been raised by their grandparents.
4. Determine the different coping strategies used by Filipino emerging adults who have received grandparent care.

Methodology

Research Design

The researchers employed a qualitative approach through the Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA) research design. According to Delve & Limpacher (2023), Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA) prioritizes a deep understanding of individual experiences, allowing participants to share their stories without the imposition of existing theories. Recognizing humans as meaning-makers, IPA acknowledges the inherently interpretive nature of understanding lived experiences. The researchers followed

Colaizzi's Method of Data Analysis in Phenomenological Research since it would help them to uncover emergent themes to understand people's experiences (Praveena, 2022). The researchers followed the seven steps of Colaizzi's Method of Data Analysis in Phenomenological Research (1) each of the transcripts was read and re-read, in order to obtain a general sense about the whole content; (2) significant statements that relate to the phenomenon under study would be extracted from transcripts; (3) formulated meanings was derived from significant statements; (4) organization of formulated meanings in to clusters of themes; (5) integrated findings into an exhaustive description (6) give description of the fundamental structure of the phenomenon; and (7) validated the findings from the study participants. Triangulation was used to validate the findings and trustworthiness of the study where multiple data sources was done such as interviews with the participant's relatives. Interview transcripts and the formulation of meanings was presented to each participant to verify the accuracy of the information. Additionally, the researcher's observations of participants were served as a third method of triangulation.

Participants

The participants of the study were 5-10 Filipino emerging adults coming from Manggahan, Commonwealth in Quezon City, which ranks the highest in terms of population out of all bases according to Philippine Statistics Authority 2015 as cited from the 2022-2024 Contingency Plan for Earthquake of the said barangay. Sampling technique used purposive sampling or finding potential respondents who fits in the criteria. The participants were chosen by the following inclusion criteria: (1) a Filipino citizen; (2) should be in ages 18 to 25 years old; (3) lived with at least one biological grandparent as their primary caregiver for a minimum of five years during childhood; and (4) currently living with grandparent.

Instrument

The researchers created a 4-item semi-structured interview guide that asked questions according to the statement of purpose which main topics are: (1) perspectives; (2) values; (3) challenges; and (4) coping. Each respondent was catered to separate one-on-one interviews at their preferred setting, time, and date where inquiries from the research questions was asked. This was done with the use of recording for documentation of audio-visual to ensure the completeness of respondents. Once data was collected, it was transcribed by the researchers for data analysis.

Results and Discussion

Table 1. Summary of Themes

Theme	Subtheme	Illustrative Quote
Autonomy	Breeding proactivity	<p>"Yung mga gawaing bahay tumutulong na din, lalo na sa paglalaba. Syempre hindi na natin i-aasa yun lalo na nasa tama at wastong gulang na din tayo bilang mga kasapi ng pamilya." (R7)</p> <p>"Yung mga household chores. Especially sa mga katulad ko na turning into adult napakahalagang bagay kasi magagamit ko yun kung mamumuhay ako ng independently." (R1)</p> <p>"Pandemic, nakikitulong naman ako sa mga gawain tulad sa tatay ko sa online sa bible studies, at ang nanay ko pag pumupunta sa events ako ang nagdidilig ng halaman." (R4)</p>
	Weighing consequences	<p>"Yung unang pagkakamali mo sa isang bagay, dapat kapag sinabihan ka na huwag na ulit-ulitin." (R6)</p> <p>"Parang yung buhay ko paulit-ulit na lang na pag gusto ko lang. Ngayon, may nagkkontrol na sakín, basta pag alam kong tama sinusunod ko." (R3)</p> <p>"Palagi mo munang pag iisipan mabuti yung decisions, kasi yung mga matatanda or lalo na si nanay sinasabi niya palagi isipin mo muna kung ano yung magiging desisyon mo hindi lang twice, thrice isipin mo nang paulit ulit if magbebenefit kaba talaga don, ano yung magiging consequences ng mga gagawin mo." (R6)</p>
Being and Courtesy	Living a spiritual Life	<p>"Pagtuturo ng halaga ng pananampalataya." (R2)</p> <p>"Ang natutunan ko sa grandparents ko, yung pag pray, lagi nilang sinasabi sakín kahit hindi ka nangangailangan, or nangangailangan ka lagi ka pa ring mag pray, ibigay mo yung faith mo kay God." (R7)</p> <p>"Laging sinasabi na magdasal sa lahat ng oras." (R6)</p> <p>"Kahit anong mangyari, dasal lagi ang kanilang paalala." (R4)</p> <p>"Unang una is prayers, kasi ano catholic, so, naniniwala ako sa power ng prayer." (R10)</p> <p>"Lumaki po talaga ako na malawak yong pag-unawa ko kasi yun po talaga yung tinuro niya sa akin simula't simula na kung ano yung ginagawa sayo ng iba, wag na wag mong gagawin sa kanila." (R2)</p> <p>"Pag may kasalanan ako sa iba na hindi ko sinasadya. My grandparents would tell me 'You need to deal with it, wag kang magtatangkang umalis because that's wrong.'" (R4)</p>
		<p>"Coforming to this strict policy, I mean mga bagay na pamahiin yung mga sinasabi nila na mga bawal, ayin maraming mga ganun. So, living with your grandparents, kailangan mo mag conform sa mga bagay na sinasabi nila." (R1)</p> <p>"Importante yung laging nagdadasal." (R3)</p> <p>"Yung mga tamang asal, kunwari may parang mali na ako or napapasobra, napagsasabihan naman, minsan nag eend up pa sa paghampas pero normal naman, napakalaking tulong kasi naging ganto ako ngayon dahil sa mga payo nila, mga pagdidisiplina." (R9)</p> <p>"Pinapakita nila sa akin yung tamang ugali at asal sa lahat ng oras." (R3)</p>
Dissonance and Endurance	<p>Conflict cause by generational gap</p> <p>Building moral character</p>	

		<p>“Natutunan ko po sa kanila yung mga dapat po lagi tayong nakikinig sa mga nakakatanda satin kasi alam nila yung mga dapat gawin tsaka sila yung mga may mas may experience kesa satin, tsaka yung mga sinasabi nila para din naman satin.” (R8)</p> <p>“Laging sinasabi samin, ‘naranasan ko na yan kaya alam ko mga yan, mga bagay na yan’ lagi niya sinasabi yun tapos ako naman parang napapa isip ako, oo nga noh. Lalo na ngayon malaki na ako dati sinasabi niya lang samin. Kapag hindi niyo inayos yung buhay niyo magiging ganto kayo, ganito ganyan. eh nagkakatotoo naman mga sinasabi ng lola ko.” (R7)</p> <p>“There are times na they are strict, yung strictness na yun it comes from a reason.” (R9)</p> <p>“Siguro yung pagless ng usap, parang akalako noon na di kami masyadong kaclose ganun.” (R9)</p> <p>“Nabubully ako, hindi ko talaga sinasabi sa kanila yon.” (R2)</p>
	Fear due to limited existence	<p>“Mas namulat ako or aware ako na anytime soon dahil nga matanda na sila they may begin na iwan nila ako.” (R10)</p> <p>“Feeling ko that time kasi kahit pinalaki ako, parang feel ko kasi mag isa lang ako ganun. Parang na ffeel ko na lonely ako, parang nagkakaroon ako ng anxiety.” (R7)</p> <p>“As a child maghahanap ka ng kalinga ng parents’ mo from their own tapos ang meron ka is yung grandparent’s mo which is iba sa makikita mo sa ibang bata. Everyday challenge na iisipin mo anytime mawawala sila. So iba yung pag aalala mo, hindi siya palaging comforting kasi hindi mo masasabi kelan sila mawawala so nag aalala ka rin every day.” (R10)</p>
Freedom	Practicing self-expression	<p>“Usually, kapag nagagalit si lola. Ang una kong ginagawa is syempre iniwasan ko muna na ma- expose sa kanya lalo na kapag nagagalit siya like nagwawala siya lalayo ka muna. So, after niya magalit pag kumalma na siya tsaka mo na siya kausapin.” (R1)</p> <p>“Bonding with them para makapag-cope up pa rin sa mga iniisip ko at night na baka mawala sila ganun. Paggising ko sa umaga nagkakaroon kami ng small talks over breakfast or minsan sa dinner ganun.” (R10)</p> <p>“Syempre since safe space ko nga yung room ko, naroon lang ako nagddrawing.” (R2)</p>
	Nurturing mindfulness	<p>“Mas maaga akong namulat na face the life to its fullest na i-enjoy bawat moment kasi pwede siyang mawala sayo, so enjoy lang.” (R10)</p> <p>“Natulungan niya ako sa stress kasi pagka sobrang toxic na nung surroundings dapat nagrerest muna para marefresh yung utak natin para alam yung dapat gawin.” (R8)</p>

Theme 1: Autonomy

This theme highlights the perspectives of Filipino emerging adults receiving grandparent’s kinship care in breeding proactivity and weighing consequences. These are crucial in self-discovery that allows autonomy. By understanding what truly matters, building confidence in choices, these emerging adults can independently approach life, set goals aligned with their values, and make decisions that lead to a fulfillment.

“Breeding proactivity”. Values influence an individual’s perspective on their current situation. The first step in building values is to be proactively committed to creating change. More than half of the Filipino emerging adults receiving grandparent’s care admits the importance of reflection and taking action in choosing practical decisions that could help them in later adulthood. In fact, self-reflection should be practiced at any age because of several benefits such as it breeds fresh perspectives, it builds self-awareness, and improves decision making skills (Perry E., 2022). Grandchildren learned to reciprocate the act of helping throughout the years of receiving help in household chores, emotional support, and financial aid from grandparents. They perceive doing household chores as an important task that a family member should do and can be beneficial skill in becoming a responsible adult. Aside from household chores, grandparents were also able to extend emotional support to their grandchildren in various ways such as communicating with them in times of hardship, putting their grandchildren to sleep, and showing encouragement in their chosen path. A study on grandchildren and their grandparents have shown that the level of emotional closeness serves an important factor for both the development of well-being and successful aging. The emotional closeness of individuals in a relationship creates a reciprocal influence and willingness to stay together throughout life (Duflos M., et al., 2022). In addition, grandparents work as hard as parents in providing the daily necessities of their grandchildren such as housing, food, water, and clothing.

“Weighing consequences”. As mentioned, the ultimate goal of a family is to prepare children to be responsible adults. The primary method for doing so is to give trust and allow them to experiment and set expectations in a safe environment under guidance (Savage, C., 2023). The Filipino emerging adults receiving grandparent’s care weighs the consequences of their actions. They take time to carefully decide what to do and ask themselves if it is the right thing. If mistakes were made, grandchildren make sure that it would not be repeated.

Theme 2: Being and Courtesy

This theme captures the values formed in the lives of Filipino emerging adults who receive grandparent’s kinship care, it highlights the importance of living a spiritual life and building moral character. Raised under the loving care of their grandparents, these emerging adults reflect on how their upbringing has shaped their core values of "Being and Courtesy," forming the foundation of their spiritual lives and moral character.

"Living a Spiritual Life" holds profound commitment to spiritual practices among Filipino emerging adults receiving grandparent

kinship care. Echoes of prayers offered daily and the gentle reminders to rely on faith in everything deeply resonate with this theme. Indeed, it is the grandparents who often instill a steadfast belief in the power of prayer, which gives their grandchildren this sense of being spiritually grounded and strong. These rituals and teachings then become a haven in turbulent times—providing emerging adults with a greater connection to their faith and dependence on divine guidance. It, therefore, emphasizes that faiths are an integral part of everyday life and not just supplications in difficult times. Thus, these teachings have clearly had a lasting impact, embedding a deep faith to these emerging adults that serves as a cornerstone for their spiritual well-being. According to Schaeffler (2023), "Grandparents want to live their lives and share their faith with their grandchildren; they desire to be supported in this treasured role. They hold the exclusive duty of transmitting their faith to the next generation." This is further supported by the study from Burt in 2023, in which it is shown that grandparents have been bestowed upon the responsibility of passing down their faith to their successions, whether through prayer or ministerial work. The constant encouragement of prayer, no matter the circumstance, gives these emerging adults trust and dependence on this higher power. It reinforces that prayer is not just for times of need, but is a continuous practice, which gives advice, comfort, and strength to face life. This approach—put into action by the grandparents—has given these emerging adults a strong spiritual anchor with which to stand against life's uncertainties.

"Building Moral Character" grandparents are known for being fonts or source of wisdom for lessons in integrity, respect for people, and conduct of ethical performance. They instill such values, which one day will define the choices of emerging adults and their interactions, through gentle discipline and heart-to-hearts. These teachings emphasize being empathetic, liable for one's actions, and committed to treating all things fairly and with kindness. The value of listening to elders emphasizes their greater experience and the intention behind their advice. The practical wisdom that they gained through years of lived experience, permeates daily life lessons. From decision-making strategies to conflict resolution, grandparents play a major role in equipping their grandchildren with the tools needed to move through adulthood with thought and maturity. Their advice is full of reflection and forethought, urging their grandchildren to ponder over their actions and to engage in prudent and responsible decisions. As stated in the study of Pegasus Home Health Care (2019), "There is an undeniable advantage of benefiting from the extensive life experience of your elders. Their life wisdom has undergone similar hurdles with you though at different times, and holds very valuable lessons on how to make it through today's challenges." This is further solidified by a study from LinkedIn (2023), "When we take personal responsibility for our actions, the likelihood of identifying mistakes, learning from them, and bringing needed adjustments to our behavior increases." This fosters a much healthier relationship since now they are so much more empathetic, caring, and understanding towards others. On the other hand, grandparents impart the importance of resilience to their grandchildren through the sharing of their own life stories, demonstrating how to overcome challenges and embrace change (Saini, 2023). The emphasis on accountability not only strengthens the character of these emerging adults but also prepares them for the complexities as they transition to adulthood. Thus, grandparents instill a sense of inner strength and moral fortitude in their grandchildren by teaching these values, enabling them to navigate life with confidence and ethical clarity.

Theme 3: Dissonance and Endurance

This theme explores the challenges faced by Filipino emerging adults who are raised by their grandparents. It highlights the conflict caused by generational gaps and fear due to the limited existence of their grandparents. These multifaceted challenges reflect the overarching theme of "Dissonance and Endurance," showcasing their struggle to find balance and resilience in a unique familial dynamic.

"Conflict caused by generational gaps" Grandparents often impose conservative and culturally based standards on their grandchildren, leading to disagreements over parenting practices due to generational differences. This can create a conformity strain, where young adults feel pressured to conform to their elders' expectations. The cultural generation gap in older generations often holds more traditional views compared to younger generations, influenced by demographic changes. Studies indicate that grandparents who disregard their children's parenting choices risk being cut off from their grandchildren, which underscores the importance of respecting these boundaries (Culverhouse, 2024). This diversity often leads to a clash with the rigid, traditional values upheld by older generations, particularly in areas such as immigration and social values (Frey, 2018). Elders are respected for their wisdom and experience, but their unfamiliarity or reluctance to engage in certain topics can create a void in family discussions. This underscores the importance of fostering open communication across generations to ensure mutual understanding and respect within the family unit. A study investigates communication dynamics between grandparents and grandchildren, highlighting how grandchildren often feel unable to express themselves due to the rigid communication styles of older generations. This generational gap in communication leads to a reluctance among grandchildren to share personal thoughts or concerns (Gong et al. 2023).

"Fear due to limited existence" Grandparents' limited existence can bring emotional burdens to children, as it is their first exposure to mortality. This can foster maturity and understanding, as children may anticipate losing their other grandparents. Reassuring them by saying "I expect Grandpa to be here for a long time" can help. If the grandparent died due to illness, the child might develop a general fear of sickness and worry about dying themselves. Grandmothers often have closer relationships with their grandchildren, intensifying the difficulty of coping with their loss. Additionally, because maternal grandmothers are typically younger, their death during childhood or adolescence may come as a surprise, further complicating the emotional processing for youths (Livings, M. et. al., 2022). The death of a grandparent, particularly a maternal grandmother, can have significant consequences for adolescents' and their mothers' mental health. A recent qualitative study found that young adults who experienced the loss of a grandparent were profoundly impacted,

changing their lifestyles, contemplating their own mortality, and altering family relationships. Factors influencing death anxiety include religiosity, gender, psychological state, and age. Children often assume their parents' fear of death is prevalent. Medical staff often encounter death anxiety from family members or staff members (Sinoff, 2018). Emotional burdens often arise from the responsibility of maximizing time with grandparents, which can be overwhelming. The absence of parents can cause profound fear among grandchildren, who rely on their grandparents for emotional support and stability. The fear of losing this relationship can trigger grief, uncertainty, and disconnection from family roots. It is important to avoid associating death with sickness and to reassure the child that you will do everything possible to keep them safe and healthy (Adcox, 2022).

Theme 4: Freedom

This theme identifies the coping strategies of Filipino emerging adults receiving grandparent's care which are to practice self-expression and nurture mindfulness. These are ways on how an individual can exercise freedom to choose actions, manage emotions, and reframe their thinking when encountering life challenges.

"Practicing self-expression." Given the challenges faced such as conflict caused by generational gap and fear due to limited existence of grandparents, grandchildren have found a way on how to effectively handle their grandparents through careful communication. Communication plays an important role in stress management. The ways for which a person communicate with themselves and others can either decrease or increase stress. When conflict arise, these emerging adults make sure to distance themselves when emotions are high. This ensures clarity in later communication where both parties can rationally give feedback to one another, avoiding the use of hurtful words that can damage the relationship. A study by Watkins in 2021 suggests that those who are effective in communication are able to express their needs, feelings, and concerns which leads to better understanding, support, and resolution of conflicts. Practicing assertiveness, active listening, and empathy strengthens positive relationships, and enhance overall well-being (Watkins, 2021). When worrying about their grandparents, grandchildren often fear the feeling of loneliness and copes by having quality time with their grandparents usually planning how to start a conversation during meals or at times when they are having a problem. This gradually improves their emotional closeness and alleviate the tendency for isolation as they practice deep understanding and cooperation with one another. According to Reach Out Australia in a 2023 article, talking can help lessen feelings of loneliness at times of struggles. Talking with someone can make a person feel a lot better by just letting it out. Aside from communication, other forms of expression such as creating an Art also helps in letting out. Art in any form has the power to momentarily distract an individual from recent struggles, specifically in alleviating symptoms of anxiety and depression (Mubasher, A., 2023).

"Nurturing mindfulness." This is the same with living in the present moment by embracing thoughts, freeing thyself from fears and worries, and to grasp full in control of the now. It lets go of the memories from the past and avoid overthinking about what could happen in the future. One of the grandchildren shared how their grandparent advices them the importance of rest when dealing with stressful situations as to refresh themselves mentally to be able to gain enough strength to continue. Taking a rest is a form of self-care that promotes self-compassion. In fact, self-compassion in practicing mindfulness is crucial, particularly when dealing with anxiety by acknowledging feelings of anxiousness and allowing yourself to feel emotions without self-criticism (Calm, 2023). Due to awareness of grandparent's age, grandchildren understood at earlier years of their life that their grandparents might leave them sooner. This made them realize to value each moment and not waste time to be able to express their love and care for their grandparents who did the same for them. As a result of this, Filipino emerging adults receiving grandparental care develops a sense of gratitude and contentment having the time to spend with their grandparents while growing up.

Conclusions

"Autonomy" nurtures proactivity and decision-making skills by providing a space for self-reflection and autonomy. Additionally, the emotional and practical support that grandparents gave creates a secure environment, allowing these young adults to focus on personal growth for later adulthood. By helping with housework, offering emotional support during hardships, and assisting financially, grandparents alleviate burdens and anxieties. Considering all these, grandparent kinship care can be a beneficial arrangement for Filipino grandchildren.

"Being and Courtesy" encapsulates a recognition of spiritual values and a commitment to ethical behavior that transcends generations. The narratives of Filipino emerging adults who received kinship care from their grandparents weave a tapestry of resilience, kindness, and moral strength, how the traditions and wisdom of their families nurture their souls and mold their character through tender guidance by their grandparents. Their experiences aid, in essence, the story of a community for which spirituality and moral lessons are intertwined to create a legacy of honesty and respect that lasts not only through childhood but extends into adulthood.

"Dissonance and Endurance" highlights the challenges they face in balancing traditional upbringing with contemporary influences. Despite differences in values and expectations, they maintain strong familial bonds despite mortality. The theme emphasizes the importance of open communication and understanding to bridge cultural gaps and maintain familial cohesion. This blend of dissonance and endurance shapes their identities and resilience in a unique family context.

"Freedom" explores the essence of being in control by revealing the importance of effective communication, mindfulness, and gratitude. It can be said that the challenges faced by emerging adults were not to be overlooked due to the existence of the active coping

strategies which allows open conversations, build stronger bonds, and acquiring psychological resilience that can gradually transform the approach of these Filipino emerging adults when encountering challenges.

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